

A case study: Integrated Geotechnical and Geophysical-ERT Investigation for Bridge Foundation of Tirana Bypass

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Abstract

In this paper briefly, is described the geotechnical and geophysical investigation for bridge foundation of Tirana Bypass. For the evaluation of geotechnical conditions of the bridge's foundations of Tirana Bypass many fields works such as drilling, trial pits, and geophysical measurements-ERT Electrical Resistivity Tomography, SPT as well as laboratory tests were completed. Furthermore, from the results of drilling, laboratory analyses, and Electrical Resistance Tomography (ERT) it is possible to define the lithological profile of the bridge's foundations. These scientific results were significant because on their basis are compiled the bridge's design from civil engineers, where the new Tirana Bypass road is planned to pass.

Keywords: Geotechnical investigation, geotechnical conditions, ERT investigation, physical-mechanical properties, bridge foundation, Tirana Bypass.

1 Introduction

The studied zone extends in the south-western part of Tirana, Albania. The designs project of Tirana bypass is a main project for the region because it connects several towns from north to south with Tirana. It connects several towns in the north and south of Tirana, without entering through the city of Tirana. For the evaluation of the geotechnical condition of Tirana bypass site, many fields works such as drilling, trial pits, geophysical measurements (ERT-Electrical Resistivity Tomography), SPT, as well as laboratory tests are conducted. In this paper are presented the results of geotechnical investigations, performed during the 2013-2014 year for Feasibility Study phase in a relation of the bridge foundation. The aim of the geotechnical study was the providing of the detailed information on lithology, geomorphology, hydrology, geotechnical condition and, finally, conclusion and recommendations for the Tirana Bypass route corridor.

2 Methodology

The study area is located the south-western part of Tirana city (the capital of Albania). In a follow-up to the initial Feasibility Study phase (conceptual phase), a detailed geotechnical investigation along the approved bypass route corridor has been carried out during the 2013-2014 year [4]. The objective of this work has been the evaluation of geotechnical conditions, geological and morphological characteristics, hydrogeological conditions, and geodynamics phenomena along said route corridor. These explorations were aimed to identify the site characteristics in sufficient detail for the development of a feasible and cost-effective road and structural design and construction. The geotechnical study has been completed based on site investigation programme proceeds through the main phases i) the desk study phase, ii) the phase of field and laboratory work, and iii) the phase of data interpretation and preparation of the geotechnical report. In this paper, are discussed the geotechnical investigations and geophysical measurements (ERT-Electrical Resistivity Tomography) for evaluation of the bridge foundation of Tirana Bypass. These surveys have included the field works and laboratory tests. As part of the main work schedule, it was first considered to perform fieldwork related to drilling and its operation. There are executed many boreholes 7.0-15.0 m deep, in-situ testing (SPT) and measurements of two-dimensional Electrical Resistance Tomography-2D ERT, [5]. Also, are carried out engineering geological and hydrogeological mapping

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on scale 1:5,000 and analysed a lot of undisturbed and disturbed specimens, suitable for identification of physical and mechanical properties of soils and rocks. The samples were taken in different levels of soils profile along the selected route of bypass alignment. Many tests have been performed to evaluate the engineering properties of all the collected soil specimens influencing the performance of the proposed road structure.

They are Grain size analysis, sieve test (ASTM D 422-02) and hydrometer test (ASTM D 2217-02), natural water content (ASTM D 2216-98), bulk density-(ASTM D 2937-00), Atterberg limits (ASTM D 4318-00), specific density (ASTM D 854-02), deformations module, Odometer test (ASTM D 2435), strengths parameters, sharing box- f, internal friction angle, c- cohesion (ASTM D 3080), uniaxial compressive test for rocks (ASTM 2938-02), standard test method of Proctor, Y_{d-max} and W_{opat} (ASTM D 1557-09) and standard test procedure of Californian bearing ratio (CBR): ASTM D 1883-7e2. It is imperative to emphasise that during the fieldwork drilling operations precise measurements of underground water levels are made. Finally, were interpreted the geotechnical data and prepared the geotechnical report.

3 Results and Discussion

In this paper are presented the results of geotechnical and geophysical investigations carried out in a southern part of Tirana for evaluation of the bridge foundation of Tirana Bypass [4].

Geotechnical Conditions: The aim of the geotechnical investigations was a determination of the site's geotechnical conditions along the proposed Tirana bypass route alignment. However, in this paper as mention above we are treating the geotechnical investigations of the bridge site's foundation. As part of the major programme firstly was considered to work in the field in the orientated profile related to a drilling operation. So, as a programmed plan in the construction, a site has been executed many boreholes (Figure. 1, 2). The boreholes were drilled from 7.0-10.0 m up to 15.0 m deep. Also, there are obtained many undisturbed soils and rocks specimens, which 31 were analysed in the laboratory. They are taken to the different level of soils profile, conform to the standard (ASTM D 1587) and in the dependence of the lithological unit of studied area. By the field and laboratories works completed along of Erzeni River terraces for evaluation of the bridge foundation, nine layers (Table 1, 2) are distinguished by different geotechnical features (Figure. 2). Starting from the top to down of soil profile the following geotechnical layers are:

Tier 1: The upper part of the cross-section is presented by vegetal soils, which have soft and high organic matter contents. This layer is 0.5 - 0.7 m thick

Layer 1/1: This is gravel-sand mixtures with little fines of the Erzen riverbed. These soils are in very loose condition and saturated by water. Based on [1], the soils are involved in "GP" group. This layer is 1.7 - 3.5 m thick.

Layer 1/2: It is represented by fill soils that are a mixing of gravels, sands, silts, and pieces of broken bricks, in very loose condition.

Layer 11: It is composed of soils, which are gravel-sand-clay mixtures and gravel-sand-silts mixtures, grey colour. The thickness of this layer ranges from 1.5 to 2.0 m up to 10.4 m. According to [1], these soils are included in "GC-GM" group.

Layer 12: The soils of this geotechnical unit are a mixture of gravel-sand soils with clay, brown to beige-brown colour. According to the geotechnical condition, they are in the joint state, without water content-dry. This layer is situated below layer 1 and has a thickness of 1.2 - 2.6 m up to 5.1 m. According to [1], these soils are included in "GC" group.

Layer 13: This layer is composed of gravel-sand-silts mixtures, grey colour. According to the geotechnical condition, these soils are in the joint state. These soils are characterized by medium underground water content-moist. The thickness of this layer ranges from 3.5 to 8.5 m (Borehole B7). According to [1], these soils are included in "GC-GM" group.

Layer 14: It is represented by inorganic clays of low plasticity with fine sands. These soils contain 6.0-8.0 % gravels. They are moist and have stiff consistency, brown to beige colours. This layer is situated below layer no.1 and has a thickness of 1.3 m. According to [1], these soils are included in "CL" group.

Layer 19: It is the weathering crust of flysch rocks, consisting of intercalation of claystone-siltstones with sandstones layers, which are highly weathered, beige to grey. It has a thickness of 1.6 - 2.7 m. According to [1], these soils are included in "CL & ML" group.

Layer 20: They are represented by soft rocks, flysch, which are a combination of thin layers of the intercalation of claystone-siltstones with sandstones layers. These rocks are situated in the lower part of the investigated lithological profile.

Table 1. The mean geotechnical properties of soils

Geotechnical Unit Nr.	Physical mechanical properties								
	W_n %	γ kN/m ³	γ_o kN/m ³	ϕ (o)	c kPA	E kPA	E_{el} kPA	SPT	
1	-	15.00	-	-	-	600	-	-	OL
1/1	-	14.50	-	-	-	450	-	-	GP
1/2	-								GP
11	32.98	20.78	26.44	39	0.00	-	-	33-37	GC-GM
12	22.10	19.22	26.46	35	12.0	16577	-	12-15	GC
13	22.60	16.34	26.35	42	0.00	-	-	-	GC
14	30.05	18.54	26.73	-	-	-	-	5-16	CL

I_n -natural water content, γ -bulk density, γ_o -Specific density, ϕ -internal friction angle, c -cohesion, E -iodometric test, E_{el} -elasticity module, SPT-Standard Penetration Test

Table 2. The mean geotechnical properties of rocks

Geotechnical Unit Nr.	Physical-mechanical properties								
	W_n %	γ kN/m ³	γ_o kN/m ³	ϕ (o)	c kPA	E 10 ⁵ kPA	E_{el} 10 ⁵ kPA	SPT	
19	17.91	20.58	26.79	28	75-120	0.401	-	48-74	Weathered Flysch
20	5.00	25.21	25.68	32	-	3.39	3.14	>100	Claystone's- Siltstones

I_n -natural water content, γ -bulk density, γ_o -Specific density, ϕ -internal friction angle, c -cohesion, E -iodometric test, E_{el} -elasticity module, SPT-Standard Penetration Test.

Figure 1. Engineering geology map of bridge foundation in Bultica area on scale 1:5 000

Figure 2. Cross section of bridge foundation in Bultica area

ERT-Electrical Resistance Tomography Results: The measured pseudo-sections are interpreted with the software Res2dinv [2], [5]. For each profile, since the topography is flat, the zero shows the surface of the earth. In cases where the topography is not flat, it can be incorporated into the inverse interpretation of apparent resistivity values to make the necessary topographic corrections to take the 2D straight resistivity section. In (Figure 3), is shown the location and true resistivity cross-section of geo-electric ERT profile, performed in Bultice village, along of the Erzeni River terrace. From the distribution of the resistivity values along this profile, it can be seen that two layers are present. High resistivity values (yellow-red colour, > 100 ohm.m) are found for the cover layer composed of soils and gravel with high resistivity values. Below this upper layer is the flysch with shallow resistivity values (< 20 ohm.m), which is the bedrock.

Figure 3. True resistivity cross-section of geo-electric ERT profile 4, Bultice Village

Finally, the data obtained from geotechnical investigations and Electrical Resistance Tomography-(ERT) were used for bridge foundations. The results indicate that the integration of the geotechnical and geophysical-ERT investigation is advantageous, because of they are very accurate according to subsurface exploration and get a low cost.

4 Conclusions and Recommendations

The study area of proposed bypass is located in the west and south of Tirana City. The geotechnical study is carried out in three phases: (a) the deskwork; (b) the field works and laboratory testing; (c) data interpretation and preparation of the geotechnical report. For the bridge foundation, were completed and executed fifteen many boreholes (7.0 - 15.0), trial pits (3.0 -5.0 m), two-dimensional profiles of Electrical Resistance Tomography (2D, ERT), SPT, engineering geological and hydrogeological mapping on scale 1:5000. To examine the physical-mechanical properties of soil profiles, a lot of undisturbed, and disturbed specimens from the trial pits were

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collected and analysed afterwards in the laboratory for geotechnical properties. Through the ERT Techniques is well determined the lithology of the underground. The resistivity values distinguish very well the upper layers with high resistivity values (soils, gravel or gravel filled with water) from the basement which is flysch with very low resistivity values. It is advisable to employ the geotechnical investigations and Electrical Resistance Tomography- (ERT) for subsurface exploration because of they are instrumental, accurate and get a low cost.

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